

TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISCURSIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS WHEN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

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Abstract

The development of discursive competence is a key component of foreign language teaching at school, enabling students to effectively participate in communication in a new language. This study examines the methods and technologies used to develop discursive competence, focusing on how modern approaches can enhance students' linguistic abilities. By integrating technology into language teaching, teachers can create a more interactive and engaging learning environment. This research used qualitative and quantitative methods to analyze the effectiveness of various tools and techniques in improving students' discursive skills. Results indicated that technology plays a significant role in enhancing students' language learning experiences, though challenges such as limited resources and teacher training remain.

Keywords: discursive competence; language teaching; educational technology; foreign language learning.

Introduction

Discursive competence includes various language functions such as arguing, narrating, and negotiating meaning, which are vital for students to actively engage in real-life communication. Technology, particularly Learning Management Systems (LMS) and other digital tools, offers new ways for students to practice and improve their skills in these areas.

Morrison (2020) defines discursive competence as the capacity to use language effectively in communication, emphasizing its importance in foreign language education. Technology's integration into schools, foreign language teaching has become more dynamic and flexible, allowing teachers to create immersive environments where students can actively engage in discussions, role-playing, and simulations that develop their communicative abilities.

Materials and types of research

This study aims to explore the most effective strategies and tools for developing discursive competence in students learning foreign languages at school. Three objectives guided the research: (1) to identify the technological tools used by teachers to enhance discursive competence, (2) to evaluate the benefits and challenges of these technologies in foreign language teaching, and (3) to gather students' perspectives on how these technologies influence their language learning experience.

Research questions

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What technological tools are used by teachers to develop students' discursive competence in foreign language learning?
2. What are the benefits and challenges of using technology for discursive competence development in school settings?
3. How do students perceive the use of technology in developing their discursive skills in a foreign language?

Participants

The study involved 15 foreign language teachers and 80 students from our school. The teachers were selected based on their use of technology in language teaching, and the students were chosen from classes

where discursive competence was actively being developed. Teachers completed questionnaires about the technological tools they used and the impact of these tools on students' learning. Students were asked about their experiences with technology in language learning, with particular emphasis on how it helped them improve their ability to communicate effectively in the foreign language.

Tools

In this study, several research tools were employed to gather data on the development of discursive competence in students when learning a foreign language. These tools included questionnaires and interviews, designed to assess both teachers' and students' experiences with the integration of technology into language teaching.

First, a questionnaire was distributed to foreign language teachers to investigate the types of technology they used to foster discursive competence in their students. The survey was divided into two sections: one for teachers who actively used technology in their language teaching, and another for those who did not. For those using technology, additional questions focused on the specific tools and platforms employed, such as interactive simulations and multimedia resources, to enhance students' discursive abilities.

Second, semi-structured interviews were conducted with teachers who actively integrated technology into their foreign language classrooms. The aim was to explore their perspectives on the effectiveness of these tools in developing discursive competence. Six teachers were interviewed, with discussions focusing on the practical benefits and challenges of using technology to enhance language learning.

Third, to gather data from students, a separate questionnaire was used. This aimed to assess students' opinions on how technology had impacted their ability to engage in discourse during language lessons. The questionnaire asked students to reflect on their experiences using digital tools and how these tools had helped improve their language proficiency, particularly in areas such as speaking and writing.

Procedure

The study focused on understanding how technology can be effectively integrated into foreign language

teaching at the school level to enhance students' discursive competence. A mixed-method approach was used, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection. The objectives were two: to identify the tools used by teachers to develop discursive competence and to assess the challenges and benefits associated with using these tools in foreign language classrooms.

Enter the questionnaire

Teachers and students from various schools were selected for participation. Questionnaires were distributed to foreign language teachers to gather data on their experience with technological tools in teaching, and semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected teachers to gain deeper insights into their use of technology. The study also surveyed students to understand their perceptions of how these tools helped them engage in discourse in the foreign language classroom.

Conducting an interview

For the qualitative portion of the study, six teachers who used technology were interviewed in-depth. Semi-structured interviews allowed for flexibility in exploring how teachers integrated technology into their classrooms and their views on its impact. These interviews were recorded, transcribed, and, in two cases, translated into English for data analysis. Interviews aimed to gather detailed insights into the advantages and disadvantages of technology use in the development of discursive competence.

Data analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires and interviews were analyzed using a phenomenological approach. This method allowed the researchers to identify common themes and patterns in the teachers' and students' experiences. The qualitative data from the interviews were coded, and several topics were classified, including the benefits of technology in language learning and the challenges associated with its implementation. The results were summarized to provide a comprehensive understanding of how technology influences the development of discursive competence in foreign language students.

Research results

The survey results revealed two groups of teachers: those who regularly used technology in their teaching to foster discursive competence and those who did not. 9 out of twenty teachers actively used technology, such as interactive platforms and multimedia resources, in their classrooms. These teachers had been integrating technological tools for two to five years and utilized them to create online content, provide interactive exercises, and facilitate student discourse.

Teachers reported spending several hours weekly designing lessons that encouraged students to practice speaking and writing. For instance, they would assign tasks like writing short essays or participating in online discussions, where students could practice language skills in an interactive setting. Meanwhile, the remaining fourteen teachers cited unfamiliarity with technological tools and a lack of time as key reasons for not incorporating them into their lessons.

The teachers who regularly integrated technology into their teaching employed a variety of tools to enhance discursive competence among students. The most frequently used technologies included:

a. Interactive platforms: Teachers used platforms like Google Classroom and Zoom to facilitate real-time discussions and presentations.

b. Multimedia resources: Videos, podcasts, and audio files were used to expose students to authentic language usage and allow them to practice listening and speaking skills.

c. Collaborative tools: Google Docs and other shared platforms enabled students to collaborate on writing tasks, providing feedback to one another and improving their discursive abilities in written form.

d. Simulations and role-plays: Digital simulations allowed students to engage in real-world language practice, where they participated in simulated conversations or role-playing scenarios.

One teacher noted, "Using multimedia tools has helped my students improve their speaking skills, as they can listen to authentic dialogues and then practice speaking in similar situations." Another teacher added that interactive platforms helped students become more confident in expressing themselves in written form through regular peer interactions.

Advantages of using technology in developing discursive competence

According to the survey, the benefits of using technology in language teaching were divided into three main groups. First, technology facilitated student-centered learning, enabling learners to engage with content tailored to their language proficiency and interests. Second, it provided flexibility, allowing students to practice discourse at any time and from any location. Third, technology simplified course management, providing teachers with tools to organize lessons, track progress, and distribute materials efficiently.

Some specific advantages mentioned by teachers and students included:

- Improved opportunities for self-paced learning and practicing discourse.
- Easy access to materials, making learning outside the classroom more convenient.
- Reduction in time and costs for creating and distributing materials, as all content was available online.
- Opportunities for students to consolidate their knowledge through online quizzes and presentations.

Students particularly appreciated the ability to complete assignments at their own pace, revise based on teacher feedback, and engage in interactive online discussions, which they found helpful for improving their discursive competence.

Disadvantages of using technology in developing discursive competence

Despite the advantages, several disadvantages were identified, categorized into three main areas: technological issues, teacher preparedness, and the effectiveness of certain features. Teachers reported problems related to unstable internet connections and technical difficulties, which occasionally hindered the effectiveness of online platforms.

Moreover, teachers emphasized the need for more training and time to become proficient in using these tools. Some teachers found the platforms' features too

complex, making it challenging to adapt them to discursive tasks. Additionally, not all features were deemed suitable for fostering discourse, particularly in activities requiring real-time interaction and spontaneity.

Student reference information and experience with technology

The study involved 50 students (20 male, 30 female), aged 13 to 17 in school-lyceum "Saulet". Of these, 24.4% used technology frequently for language learning, 46% used it occasionally, and 29.6% rarely engaged with it.

Student Feedback on using technology for discursive competence development

The majority of students (96%) reported no issues accessing online platforms outside of class, with 91.5% finding it easy to access from home. Students were generally positive about the user-friendliness of these platforms, with 91% agreeing that the layout was well-structured and easy to navigate.

Regarding communication, over 90% of students felt comfortable expressing their ideas in online forums and chatting with classmates. They also found it convenient to interact with instructors digitally. Moreover, 97% of students appreciated the inclusion of online exercises and quizzes, which they believed enhanced their learning and discourse skills.

Students also noted the importance of self-discipline and computer literacy for effective use of these tools. More than 96% indicated that they would like to use similar technology in future courses, and 93% believed their language learning had improved due to the incorporation of online platforms.

Discussion

Research Question 1: What technological tools are used by teachers to develop students' discursive competence in foreign language learning?

The development of discursive competence involves students' ability to effectively communicate in a structured and contextually appropriate manner in a foreign language. Based on the study, teachers employed several technological tools to foster discursive competence:

Content creation and course management: Teachers found the integration of various digital platforms to be helpful in creating course materials that could enhance students' discursive skills. By utilizing resources such as learning management systems (LMS) and multimedia tools, they were able to provide diverse language input. One teacher used a specific LMS to facilitate structured exercises for discursive practice, enabling students to respond to prompts in written or oral form, which encouraged them to organize their ideas logically. Similarly, the use of multimedia resources such as videos and podcasts provided real-life conversational scenarios that further promoted discursive development.

However, not all teachers found this approach effective. One teacher pointed out that merely uploading static documents did not actively engage students in discursive practice. This observation aligns with Goodwin-Jones' research, which emphasizes that while technology can facilitate resource sharing, active interaction is crucial for developing communication skills.

Interactive tools: The study highlighted the significance of interactive tools such as forums, chats, and discussion boards in promoting discursive competence. Teachers created opportunities for students to engage in online discussions, allowing for peer-to-peer interaction and real-time feedback. For instance, students participated in structured dialogues where they had to present their arguments and respond to their peers in a coherent manner. This form of interaction mimics real-life communication, which is essential for developing discursive skills.

Despite the benefits, some teachers faced challenges in organizing these interactive sessions. One teacher admitted to not knowing how to create separate discussion rooms or monitor student engagement in forums, indicating that technical training for teachers is necessary. Nevertheless, the use of forums and chats was generally regarded as an effective way to engage students in meaningful communication, providing a platform for real-time feedback and opportunities for students to refine their discursive abilities.

Research Question 2: What are the benefits and challenges of using technology for discursive competence development in school settings?

The study identified several benefits of using technology to develop discursive competence:

Facilitates student-centered learning: Technology provided a platform where students could independently practice language skills. Online discussions, structured activities, and multimedia content encouraged students to engage with the material on their own terms. This aligns with student-centered learning, as students could explore topics of interest while practicing language structures and discourse.

Learning anytime, anywhere: With technology, students could engage in discursive practice beyond the classroom. For example, one teacher reported that students frequently participated in online discussions after school hours, helping them stay engaged and continue practicing. This flexibility allowed students to improve their communication skills at their own pace.

Simplifies course management: Teachers could easily manage course content and track student progress. They appreciated how technology helped them organize discussion topics, schedule assessments, and facilitate group work.

However, there were notable challenges:

Technological limitations: Some teachers and students encountered difficulties with internet connectivity and system performance, which hindered their ability to use technological tools effectively. Teachers expressed frustration when technical glitches interrupted online discussions or limited access to multimedia resources.

Teacher preparedness: Not all teachers felt adequately prepared to use technology to enhance discursive competence. Some lacked the necessary training to utilize interactive tools effectively, leading to feelings of insecurity about integrating technology into their teaching practices.

Balancing traditional and technological methods: While technology offers several tools for facilitating communication, some features were not ideal for all students. For instance, some students preferred face-to-

face discussions over online forums, indicating that technology alone may not be sufficient for developing discursive competence. Teachers recognized that a balance between traditional and technological methods was essential.

Research Question 3: How do students perceive the use of technology in developing their discursive skills in a foreign language?

Students generally had a positive attitude towards the use of technology in language learning. They appreciated the ease of access to materials and communication platforms both inside and outside the classroom. Key findings include:

Positive attitudes towards online discussions: Many students reported that they found online discussions helpful for practicing discursive competence. They enjoyed sharing their ideas and receiving feedback from both peers and teachers. This finding is supported by research from Perkins and Pfaff Mann, who argue that online communication tools enhance peer interaction and provide a valuable space for language practice.

Increased confidence in language use: Most students agreed that using technology to practice discursive skills helped boost their confidence in using the foreign language. They valued the opportunity to engage in structured online exercises and discussions, which helped them develop their ability to communicate effectively.

However, some students expressed a preference for face-to-face discussions over online platforms. While they found online tools useful, they felt that in-person interactions allowed for more natural communication and immediate feedback. This suggests that a blended approach, combining both online and offline activities, may be the most effective method for developing discursive competence in foreign language education.

Conclusion

The use of technology in developing discursive competence among students has proven to be both effective and challenging. Teachers employed a variety of tools, such as content management systems and interactive forums, to enhance students' language skills. The flexibility and accessibility of technology provided significant benefits, particularly in facilitating student-centered learning and improving course management.

However, technological challenges and the need for better teacher preparation highlight the importance of ongoing support and training for educators. Overall, students responded positively to the integration of technology into language learning, though many emphasized the need for a balance between online and traditional methods.

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